

GARDEN ART FROM PAST TO PRESENT

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Abstract: Throughout history, human beings have organized the environment they live in according to their own purposes and wishes. However, when the changes made in the environment are made by using vegetation, relaxing, relaxing and eye-caressing spaces have emerged. Especially in hot countries, due to the climate, pools, small streams, fountains have added diversity to these areas and caused the formation of beautiful gardens.

The size of the gardens, the choice of location, the materials used and the types of plants have become prestigious and showy and have gained an important dimension over time. As desires have changed, the structure of gardens, the materials used and the areas emphasized have varied from country to country.

This article is being investigated how garden art has developed throughout history in various cultures and what has influenced it.

Keywords: Garden Art, Garden design, Landscape Planning, Vegetation, Garden Building Elements, Gardens of the World, Garden Culture.

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1. Introduction

Landscape applications and landscaping studies date back to prehistoric times. However, since the first people had very limited use, purpose and opportunities, the changes they brought to the natural structure were not large. The very small-scale landscaping that began with the birth of humanity has developed consciously or unconsciously, positively or negatively throughout history, leading to the development of today's large-scale landscaping concept (Korkut, 1995). Landscape effects occur whenever people are in contact with the environment. This effect can be observed not only in landscapes from past periods, but also from the past to the present by following the change over time. Landscape is an important way for people to connect with their environment by reflecting their history, identity, past and lifestyle (Nurlu, 2021).

At the same time, in modern life, people's activities in urban common spaces mirror the cultural, social and economic structures of those cultures and societies (Deniz, 2005).

The desire for a comfortable environment, cooling down and resting has led people to change and organize the environment around them. The use of plants alongside architectural structures to meet these desires has yielded very good results. The gardens that were created have gained value over time and have begun to express fame and wealth. Throughout history, gardens that will be examples have been created in various countries and have formed the basis of botanical gardens that will be established in the future.

Botanical gardens not only displayed plants, but also began to exhibit plant breeding practices and create valuable collections (Çelik et al., 2018).

In addition, botanical gardens, which are versatile educational and recreational areas, can be found even in small settlement areas of all socio-economically developed countries today (Bramwell, 1987).

In today's cities, people affected by the pace of modern life prefer green areas, gardens and parks where they can do various activities in order to live a healthy life both physically and spiritually (Uyanık, 2022). In this study, gardens that have existed in the world throughout history were examined and the formation, development, direction and time-dependent change of garden art were determined.

2. Material and Method

The material of this study consists of gardens in various countries. The structure and purpose of the gardens, which have changed over time, have been examined.

In the ancient times: Egypt, Ancient Iran, Mesopotamia, Greek and Roman Garden Art; Medieval Garden Art, Islamic Garden Art, Renaissance Garden Art, English and Ancient Turkish Gardens, Far East and Russian Gardens were discussed.

A conclusion was drawn based on all the research findings.

3. Definitions

Garden design begins with the arrangement of the landscape. Advancedly designed gardens have formed the basis of garden art. Botanical knowledge is required for the correct selection of plants used in gardens. These are information such as the soil, temperature, light, and water requirements of plants.

The concept of "botany", derived from the French word "botanique", means plant science (TDK, 2024).

Gardens created in various countries of the world have become the ancestors of botanical gardens.

Botanical gardens; contain different natural beauties and help people to recognize many plants growing in different climates (Müminoğlu etc., 2018).

However, compared to garden art, botanical gardens need to be planned and arranged more carefully and specifically in order to be suitable for their purpose. Botanical gardens; are established with the aim of protecting plant species that are in danger of extinction, ensuring the continuation of their generations, as well as using them in education and training, and conducting scientific research on plants (Müminoğlu, 2018).

4. Historical Development

4.1. The importance of examining historical gardens

The foundation of contemporary and professional gardens is based on old historical gardens. There are some influences and similar aspects of old gardens in new gardens. In this respect, in order to understand today's gardens, it is of great importance to examine and research the old gardens that form the basis of these gardens (Korkut, 1995).

At the same time, the historical dimension of landscapes, that is, the changes they have undergone over time, must be revealed. Therefore, in order to reveal the landscape character of an area, the traces of past landscapes must be determined in the protection, management and planning studies of landscapes (Nurlu, 2021).

4.2. Ancient Garden Art

I. Egyptian Garden Art:

Ancient Egyptians had a high culture and civilization between 2000-4000 BC and reached the peak in the art of garden arrangement. Egyptian garden art was the beginning of the garden arts that would emerge after it. Garden art in Egypt developed mainly in the temples and royal gardens and mansions belonging to the pharaohs. Ancient Egyptian gardens, which were used as cool and shady outdoor living spaces and recreation areas, also reflected the power and strength of the pharaohs (Korkut, 1995).

The first garden example was built in 2720 BC. The formal gardens with small entrances were symmetrically arranged and had high walls due to climate conditions and protection. In the tomb paintings, which were customary even at that time, acacias and palm trees were depicted in symmetrical rows around lotus pools (Egyptian Gardens, 2023).

The high walls that closed to the outside were for protection from external dangers and the sand spray of the desert, and for providing a cool and shady place. Large water shows were held for two

purposes: religious effect and water storage. It was a religious tradition to sail the dead in boats in large pools. Its use as a water storage was for irrigation purposes. In order to provide a formal order in the plantation, care was taken to plant the plants in a certain row. Rhythmic planting was applied especially on the roadsides and poolsides. In the gardens of civilians, houses were built in the shape of a "U" or "L" and the garden was arranged in the form of a courtyard. This system is still used in Anatolia (Korkut, 1995)

Egyptian Gardens, 2024.

II. Ancient Iranian Garden Art:

In Iran, since religion did not have much influence at the beginning, inscriptions rather than tombs provide information about garden art. The use of materials such as brick and adobe prevented the structures from reaching the present day. However, with the use of stone over time, valuable works have survived to the present day (Korkut, 1995).

Iranian gardens were formed by geometrically shaped pools filled with water, canals extending from them on four sides and finally high walls surrounding the living spaces (Klark, 2008). Since a religious movement close to Naturalism (Zoroastrianism) began to be effective in Iran under the influence of Egypt and Assyria, garden art focused on nature developed. Later, the four-part garden arrangement called Chahar Bag emerged. The main feature of this arrangement is that the two main axes dividing the garden intersect each other and that there is a body of water in each part that emerges. In Iranian gardens, as in other Islamic gardens, there are four features: water (irrigation, rest), shade (cooling), flowers (color, smell) and music (pleasure to the ear).

Persian Gardens, 2024.

III. Mesopotamian Garden Art:

As is known, Mesopotamia is the area extending from the south of Lake Van to the Persian Gulf. In 5000 BC, the south of Lake Van

was a swamp. The overflow of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers made this area unsuitable for cultivation. The Sumerians were the ones who made this area suitable for cultivation: they connected the two rivers and established a drainage system. This deep knowledge and skill were also effective in the development of garden art. In Mesopotamian civilizations, importance was also given to different materials. The grounds of gardens and buildings were decorated with plant motifs. This decoration continued until the Renaissance (Korkut, 1995).

Unlike the Egyptians, the palaces were magnificent because they built the works of art for the heads of state and the king. However, with the rise of Babylon in the 6th century BC, the city was divided by wide streets intersecting each other and hanging gardens were spread out (Mesopotamian Gardens, 2023).

The most famous gardens among ancient civilizations are the "Hanging Gardens of Babylon", built by Nabuccodon for his Persian wife and known as one of the seven wonders of the world. However, there are no examples that have survived to the present day from the Babylonian civilization, which was built of brick and was exposed to natural disasters such as earthquakes and floods as well as invading tribes. According to the writings of Greek historians Strabo and Diodorus, these gardens covered an area of 4-5 decars and rose like a theater amphitheatre. The arches of the highest floor, where the platform where the garden was built, were 50 arm lengths long. The main garden was located on the top terrace and was waterproofed with a mat plastered with an asphalt-like substance. On top of this, there were two rows of bricks arranged on mortar. A layer made of lead was spread on the top. Some construction elements were added to the structures in order to be able to support these roofs, where soil was piled up at a depth where large trees could grow. The inside of the load-bearing brick columns were hollowed out for the roots of large trees to develop. These terrace gardens had cool corners reserved for entertainment, fountain pools with moving water, shade-giving trees and decorative flowers. These gardens, which had a view towards Babylon and the river, resembled a lush green hill from a distance (Korkut, 1995).

Garden of Babylon, 2024.

IV. Greek Garden Art

Garden art developed during the time of Alexander the Great and later rulers. This was influenced by wartime encounters with Assyrian, Persian, and Egyptian culture. Creating special gardens for great masters of philosophy was also very important in terms of experiencing religious and social influences. The creation of home gardens developed especially after contacts with the East. The

courtyard with columns was surrounded by high walls and closed to the outside (Şişman and Gültürk, 2015).

As in other ancient civilizations, gardens in Greek civilization were not only organized by religious beliefs, but also influenced social and cultural life. At first, temples were the focal point in garden art, and all development occurred around them. Later, temples were abandoned to worldly uses. Since garden design elements were made of non-durable materials, they could not survive to the present day. Considering that people mostly spent their lives outdoors, gymnasiums and agoras were included. These were areas where all kinds of intellectual and physical activities were carried out. Safa Gardens were organized in this period. Greek Safa Gardens gave examples that reached their peak in Rome. The garden area was expanded, and large lands began to be planned with all kinds of structures and settlement complexes. The effect of the climate was taken into account in open green areas; gardens were planned in a way that would provide coolness for people in hot weather. Atriums and peristyle courtyards were established for this purpose. Atrium - is an open-topped, room-like space at the entrance of the house, and water is drained from a gutter on the ceiling to the pool in the middle.

Atrium, 2024.

A more developed version of the peristyle atrium is the courtyard type surrounded by columns.

Peristil, 2024.

Another important attempt of the ancient Greeks in garden art was that they pioneered the cultivation of flowers in pots for the first time and then in commercial flower cultivation. For this purpose, annual flowers symbolizing the untimely death of Aphrodite's lover Adonis began to be grown in pots. Importance was given to the cultivation of flowers such as lilies, narcissus, violets, cyclamens and hyacinths, and the perfumery industry first began in this period (Korkut, 1995).

V. Roman Garden Art

Since the Romans were a military nation, their livelihood was completely dependent on rural areas at first, then urban life began to accelerate. The Romans gave great importance to afforestation by creating large outdoor areas in urban life. They established outdoor courtyards with atriums and peristyle courtyards in houses, and also indoor gardens called “domus” in rich houses. They gave importance to climatic effects by allocating a large space to green cover in gardens and outdoor areas. In this period, the art of shaping plants by pruning began for the first time. In outdoor arrangements, not only ornamental plants but also fruit trees that provided benefits were used (Korkut, 1995).

Since the settlements of the cities were in a grid form, the houses consisted of rooms opening onto the courtyard and an open courtyard in the middle. Shade was created by using large columns in the garden and vegetation was used in the inner courtyard. Broad-leaved trees planted outside protected the houses from noise, dust, wind and sunlight. The vegetation in the garden was increased by using pots and raised plant cushions. Therefore, the Roman contribution to garden art was mostly through green areas created around buildings used for social and cultural purposes and high-class villa gardens (Roman Gardens, 2023).

Roman Garden Art, 2024.

4.3. Medieval Garden Art

After the disintegration of the Roman Empire, the struggle between the feudal lords in the Middle Ages forced the cities to be united, and it became impossible to establish large gardens in united cities. In addition, the Christian fanaticism of the Middle Ages deprived people of the opportunity to meet their recreational needs, to spend time on their daily lives, and to think about pleasure and enjoyment. For this reason, pleasure gardens were seen very rarely and only in churches, monasteries and castles (Korkut, 1995).

In the monastery gardens, high walls, square grass areas and surrounding walkways are intended for the prayers to wander around and add harmony to their religious thoughts. In general, small puddles or small pools provide simple beauty and peace, as well as symbolizing the moon and cleanliness (Klark, 2008).

Various types of plants were grown by priests in temple gardens and monasteries, and from time to time, various studies were conducted on plants. For example, Mendel, a clergyman, revealed his famous law, which bears his name, as a result of his studies on plants in such places, or medical students grew plants used for treatment purposes in gardens. The foundation of botanical gardens

was laid in such gardens, although not in the current sense (Özkan, 2001).

At that time, functional planning was applied in monastery and castle gardens rather than aesthetics. The gardens were used for religious meetings and recreation. Flowers, medicinal plants, vegetables and fruits were grown in the gardens, and a checkerboard parceling system was used surrounded by fences. In the late Middle Ages, as a result of political and cultural developments, high protective walls were demolished, and artificial hills were covered with meadows over time and served recreational purposes.

4.4. Islamic Garden Art

The concept of ‘Çahar- Bağ’ (meaning four-garden in Persian) specific to Islamic gardens creates a four-sided garden. It symbolizes the four sides of the world with channels flowing from the fountain or pool in the center to the four sides. In some cases, these pools are placed on four sides and connected to the center. Those walking in the garden hear the sound and coolness of the water and are under its calming and relaxing effect. A sense of wholeness prevails everywhere. This feeling forms the basis of Islamic culture, architecture and garden art. Islamic gardens represent simplicity, cleanliness and harmony (Klark, 2008).

Islamic culture and art, beyond belonging to a specific country or people, emerged as a unique art that matured on the cultural and artistic traditions of various civilizations. In the formation of Islamic garden art, the hot and dry climate conditions and social traditions of the countries where Islam spread, as well as religious philosophy, played a major role. The Islamic garden concept spread first to Japan and then to all of Europe through the Andalusian Umayyads in the 9th and 13th centuries A.D. The most characteristic examples of Islamic gardens that have survived to the present day are the Al Kasar in Seville, the Generalife and Elham palace gardens in Grenada. In these gardens, the influence of the peristyle and atriums in Rome, courtyard complexes surrounded by closed walls and passed from one to the other, can be seen (Korkut, 1995).

Due to the effect of climate, two elements in the garden - water and shade - are of vital importance for those who want to rest. At the same time, water symbolized the flow and continuity of life. In addition, camellia, benches, and pergolas, which are generally located either in the middle or at the end of the garden, were often built by the water to avoid being affected by the hot climate. The order and harmony between the structure (pool, building, pergola) and the plant in Islamic gardens represent unity (Klark, 2008).

An example of Islamic gardens that have survived to the present day, one of Timur's most beautiful gardens, "Gulbagh" (Rose garden), showed a formal and symmetrical planning feature with its perpendicular paths, rhythmically arranged square-shaped pools and channels connecting them. Another memorial garden is the Taj-Mahal, built by Shah Jahan in Agra in 1631 for his deceased wife.

The marble mausoleum, planned under the influence of Islamic thought, symbolizes tranquility and death with the calm water surface in front of it and the cypresses around it; and the longing for life and the fluidity of life with the colorful flower borders and the movement of the clouds reflected in the water.

Taj Mahal, 2024.

Florence, 2024.

4.5. Renaissance Gardens

The Renaissance is the era of rebirth that provided the transition from the dark and oppressive period of the Middle Ages to the modern world. The foundation of the Italian Renaissance gardens dates back to ancient Greece. Because the garden first gained a character that merged with the human spirit in ancient Greece. In Renaissance gardens, the garden and architecture (exterior-interior) are intertwined and it is unthinkable to separate them from each other (Korkut, 1995).

General characteristics of garden art of this period:

- Gardens were made for people and honored people,
- Garden arrangements were made based on intuition and were aimed to relax people,
- Taking the climate into account, places with a view on the hillsides of settlements were chosen,
- Terracing was made in sloping areas with importance given to naturalness,
- Permanence was aimed by choosing water, stone and evergreen trees,
- Plants shaped with sharp lines or geometric forms were planted around stairs, statues, pergolas and gazebos (Italian Renaissance Gardens, 2023).

Italian Renaissance gardens are examined in 3 periods:

a) Florence Villa Period, 1450-1503:

The first garden architect of this period was Leon Batista Albert. He created garden villas that were a mixture of Classical and Middle Ages and did not fully carry the spirit of the Renaissance.

The main principles are as follows: the villa should be established in a place that has a dominant view of the city and the countryside; the villa should be approached from the garden with slightly sloping ramps; the garden should open to the surroundings with wide viewing terraces; the garden plan should be simple, formal, and partially symmetrical according to a central axis; it should be avoided to give the garden a gloomy feature. Some facilities should be established in the garden for sunbathing and shade. For example, open-light galleries for sunbathing; pergolas covered with vines, roses, ivy, camellias, etc. were used for shade.

b) The Era of Architects (Roman Renaissance Era), 1503- 1573:

The most important architects of this period are Bramante and Raphael. The simple, elegant, small villas and gardens in Florence turned into excessive luxury and ostentation in Rome and reached the peak of magnificence. In this period, villas were built on large, sloping lands. In the gardens, terraces of different levels were connected to each other with facilities such as walls and steps.

The principles regarding the arrangement of the gardens are as follows: the dimensions were kept very large; the land features that would highlight the villa and garden location were taken into consideration; architectural facilities such as terraces and steps were planned to be dominant in the garden; the garden was used as a museum where classical sculptures were exhibited; water was used in a very abundant and dynamic manner in large-scale cascades, pools and channels.

The most important gardens of this period are; Villa d'Este (extant today, attracting attention with its water facilities), Villa Madama, Villa Caprarola, Villa Lante (an example that shows that nature and garden can come together).

c) Baroque Period, 1573-1773: During this period, materials were used in a way that was contrary to their character and expressive power. Gardens developed as areas that were oriented towards luxury and ostentation rather than being a place to live in. Contrary to the first two periods, gardens began to be opened to the public and became popular. On the other hand, the harmony between the building and the garden also decreased, that is, the relationship between the interior and exterior was broken. It is possible to list the main features of gardens as order, clarity, balance, uniformity and surprise. Water was generally used in the form of stagnant water channels, and geometrically shaped artificial pools were always preferred. Plants were pruned by giving them different shapes. Shrubs and trees also functioned more like sculptures, and flowers were planted in geometrically shaped parterres. Labyrinth examples created with evergreen plants are typical of this period. The most important examples of gardens are Villa Real, Villa Garzoni and Villa Albani (Korkut, 1995).

4.6. English Garden Art

English gardens initially bore the traces of Islamic gardens. By planting water-loving plants such as iris and kala around artificial long and narrow channels flowing in divided areas, a synthesis was created to the English style (Klark, 2008).

In the 16th century, Italian Renaissance Gardens were imitated and copied in English Gardens. "Saint James Park" and "Greenwich Park" were established by Le Notre according to Baroque principles. Later, a reaction arose in people against the boring pressure of formal life, and a movement towards naturalism began. In the 18th century, the landscape in England resembled a natural park. The formal arrangement style was contrary to the natural landscape and climatic conditions in England. Facilities such as walls, fences, canals and parallel roads that bordered the parks were removed, and the park was opened to nature. The still waters were given the opportunity to flow freely as in nature. Instead of formal pools, informal natural lakes were built; large architectural and constructional facilities such as terraces, walls, and stairs were not included. Trees were left to grow naturally. The garden was given liveliness, movement, and a natural appearance with plants of different colors in all four seasons of the year. Straight and diagonal roads that intersected each other at right angles were removed, and the routes were adapted to the natural contours of the land. These principles of the English garden style form the basis of landscaping studies today (Korkut, 1995).

Greenwich Park, 2024.

4.7. Old Turkish Gardens

Since the Turks were attached to the land, they established formal and informal connections with the land. In informal connections, the person wants to be in a close relationship with his garden, on the same level as it; to sit in the greenery, to feel close to nature, to see himself as a part of nature. The person has also established a formal connection with nature with a fearful respect. He has adopted the appearance of being separate from nature and only serving it and helping himself. Due to its location, the Turkish garden has also been influenced by the gardens that came before it or were established in nearby areas. The idea of a "Garden of Eden" has become ideal. These gardens have been the most important factor in determining the form of formal and informal relationships with nature.

With the adoption of Islam by most Turkish tribes, the art of garden arrangement brought a new dimension to the human-nature relationship and developed with the hope of creating and living in this world as heaven. Courtyards, pools, fountains and canals were used in these gardens. During the reign of the Sultans, palaces were built in different regions to be used in different seasons and gardens were created around them. Tulips, which were mostly planted in gardens, gave their name to the first half of the 18th century. In the period following this period, expectations from the garden changed and the outdoor lifestyle also affected garden

design. The opportunity to live outdoors showed that the garden came before the house for the Turks. The water in the garden was always used in a flowing form. The reason for this was that it appealed to both the eye and the ear and benefited from its coolness (Evyapan, 2011).

However, in Turkish gardens, large-scale gardens belonging to administrators and wealthy people were influenced by the West and gradually moved away from Turkish characteristics. Large cities were most affected by Western influence. Thus, while existing gardens changed shape with new arrangements, newly established ones were also built with these different rules. For example; in the 1720s, Çelebi Mehmet Efendi was greatly influenced by the Palace of Versailles in Paris and, under the influence of Grand Vizier Nevşehirli İbrahim Pasha, he had the "Sadabat Pavilion" built next to the Kağıthane Stream in 1722. Although the garden of the pavilion resembled the gardens of the Versailles palace, it reflected Turkish characteristics with its livable layout and extremely sensitive use of water. Western influence was particularly evident during the reign of Selim III. During this period, the Beşiktaş and Çırağan Yalı Palaces were enlarged to large sizes and the gardens were also put into a formal order. Other palace gardens that lost their identity the most under the influence of the Baroque Period are "Beylerbeyi", "Dolmabahçe", and "Yıldız Palace Gardens". Symmetry, axis and geometric shapes were introduced into these naturally formed informal gardens (Korkut, 1995).

Sadabat Pavilion, 2024.

4.8. Far Eastern Garden Art

The understanding of garden arrangement in Far Eastern countries is completely opposite to the understanding in Western countries, especially France and Italy. Gardens in the Far East generally represent a small sample of a piece of nature. According to Chinese thought, a garden is a composition consisting of plant material, rock and water. The first garden art in the Far East was born by bringing these elements together in China. Garden (Shan-Shui) consists of two words in Chinese, meaning mountain and water. The Chinese built artificial informal lakes of 10 km in diameter in palace gardens, reviving the sea or ocean, and decorated their edges with large pieces of rock. The most striking feature of Chinese gardens was that, despite their large dimensions, they gave importance to privacy and introverted living.

Another important feature is the pavilions established in different parts of the garden to serve different purposes. These were decorative resting units with tile roofs of different colors. In Chinese gardens, inanimate materials such as stone, mosaic, and sand were used as ground covering rather than grass plants.

However, giving these inanimate materials an appearance as if they were alive was specific to Chinese garden art. For example, obtaining a flowing water surface by properly combing inanimate materials was an art. The stones and rocks used in the gardens had symbolic meanings. They served as sculptural elements belonging to nature. Gardens where gravel, stones, and rocks are used, which are established under the name of rock gardens today, are the heritage of Chinese garden art (Korkut, 1995).

According to the ancient Chinese tradition, four basic things are needed to turn an ordinary area into a corner of paradise. These are: clarity, diversity, privacy and a sense of home. By clarity, it is meant that the planned area is not complicated and has simplicity that makes it easy to find direction. Diversity is provided by the specialness and attractiveness of each area. Privacy for the Chinese means not only surprise or sudden change, but also secret and mystery. The sense of home means providing comfort and convenience for every visitor (Leshinskaya, 2009).

Chinese Garden, 2024.

Japanese Garden Art began in the 15th century AD, developing together with Buddhism and under the influence of Chinese creativity. Japanese gardens are an idealized form of nature with a symbolic understanding. Wells and water basins used for decorative and emotional purposes are partially hidden in the garden by decorating them with trees, bushes, bamboo canes and flowers. Old, stunted, crooked and knotted plants are carefully placed in the garden. Monochrome color (shades of green) dominates the garden. Lakes in Japanese gardens represent glaciers and crater lakes or the Chinese ocean, depending on the character of the landscape. Oceans are represented by placing large sea rocks on the front of the lake in the garden and spreading fine beach sand in front of them. Some parts of the lake are hidden with rocks, trees, bushes and flowers. Water usually enters the lake in the form of a waterfall or river. Wooden and stone bridges built in the form of arches over rivers and lakes reflect in the water and form a complete circle.

In the Far East, gardens were seen as symbols of the prosperity of nations. In times of peace and abundance, large-scale beautiful gardens were established. However, in Japan, the garden was never seen as a symbol of wealth.

There are 4 main garden styles in Japanese Gardens:

a) Dry Stone Gardens-The main elements are stone and rock. All the expressions that are wanted to be emphasized in the garden are represented with these elements. For example; a strong water expression can be given with stone, gravel and sand.

b) Water Garden-There is a circulation system that goes around the water facilities. Bridges are frequently seen in this order.

c) Garden of Poets-They are simple, literary gardens that emerged completely under the influence of arts. They are small in size.

d) Tea Garden-They are important in terms of being places where the Japanese pass from the outside world to the inside world. These gardens emerged as a result of romanticism and social life (Korkut, 1995).

Japanese Garden, 2024.

4.9. Russian Gardens

The first Russian gardens were mainly monasteries from the 11th to the 16th centuries. In the 16th century, palace gardens gained importance. Of these, the Moscow Kremlin gardens, Yauza and Moscow River gardens hold an important place. The most famous garden of that time was built by the request of Vasiliy Dmitriyevich, the son of Dmitriy Donskoy, and was named 'Vasilyevskiy Sad'. During the reign of Peter the Great, importance was given to the construction of large park gardens. Although the gardens of the 18th century resembled European gardens, there were some differences. For example, they were softer and more natural in appearance than French gardens. The neat park layout and paths suddenly turned into hidden paths, leading to either a lake or a flower garden. The most famous garden of this century is considered to be the Demidov Garden. 2000 species of plants were grown here. The garden was arranged in a neat amphitheater shape and terraced. Many stone greenhouses were built in the garden area and different varieties such as pineapple, grapes, palm trees, tropical plants were grown. In the 19th century, Russian park-gardens gained more importance; along with the natural environment, there were also Egyptian pavilions, historical artifacts, Chinese pergolas in the area (Leshinskaya, 2009).

In previous times, the arrangement of parks and gardens in Russia was related to the arrangement of individual parks or palace gardens. Nowadays, these studies are carried out in a broader scope, paying attention to landscaping and the display of historical structures. Before the 20th century, parks in Russia were mostly built in the courtyard style. They contained houses, barns, and garages where construction equipment was left. In the first half of the 20th century, the concept of parks and gardens changed with the formation of city parks as public areas. Here, importance was given to sports activities, education and ecology, recreation and children's areas. In addition, architectural and engineering plans began to be made. (Grishina, 2013).

Until the 16th century, flowers and fruits were grown in the monastery gardens. The planting areas within the monastery area represented paradise. The planting areas outside the monastery borders were considered divine gardens. In the Russian Empire, many regular, planned areas were created in the gardens of the palaces. For example, in 1635, a special garden was built for the children of King Mikhail Födorovich in the Teremnogo palace. During the reign of King Alexei Mikhailovich, the largest garden was in Ismaylov. These gardens were places where architects, gardeners and masters demonstrated their knowledge. There were flower carpets, secret paths and camellias, water fountains and statues. In the 18th century, during the reign of Pyotr I, great importance was given to parks and they were planned as public areas for the first time. One of these was the 'Letniy Sad', which was started to be built at the request of Pyotr I. The garden contained statues, shaped and pruned bushes and trees, parallel avenues with trees and fountains. There was also a bird and animal shelter near the house and a greenhouse where exotic flowers were grown. Towards the end of this period, more emphasis was placed on ostentation in gardens built around Moscow.

After this, the style of the gardens changed completely and emphasis began to be placed on the natural flow in line with the English style. In the 'Bogoroditskiy' park with a different planning, the architect tried to create ruined structures with sand and pieces of wood, giving way to surprises, and created ponds and waterfalls close to the natural structure by bringing water from the nearby area through channels (Pyatnov, 2013).

Summer Garden, 2024.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

When the historical development of Garden Art is examined, it is possible to say that gardens were first made with the desire for comfort and rest, and then the effect of ostentation, prestige and wealth was added to this. As people see different examples of gardens made in different countries and times, they have created gardens with new structures by challenging their imagination.

Egyptian gardens belonging to the early age garden art are known for the symmetrical and sequential planting and the creation of formal gardens. Gardens built behind high walls based on the warm climate and introverted lifestyle, as well as the courtyard-shaped inner gardens of the common people, were also used in gardens to be built in different countries in the future.

In gardens, the life and emphasis on life, which is more specific to the Islamic world, was expressed with water. The water channels

extending from four sides of the garden were connected to pools of various sizes and shapes, giving movement and meaning to the water. The effect of the hot climate is shown by the use of broad-leaved trees in terms of creating shade. The use of water was also important in the Christian world. Water, which was used for spiritual cleansing, was generally used in stagnant form in gardens. The water kept in such pools also had the purpose of irrigation.

In the hanging gardens, which were famous in Mesopotamian civilizations and whose fame has survived to our time, the terracing method of planting plants was used. In addition to various pools and fountains, the dominance of the landscape also gained importance.

In Greek garden art, the use of columns and the enlargement of the area were not only for religious purposes, but also for the development of social and cultural activities. In addition, the new activity that would affect the understanding in the future was the planting of plants in pots. This phenomenon triggered the sale and trade of plants.

In addition to intensive greening, the Romans began to shape plants by pruning them and gave importance to more useful plants with edible fruits.

During the Middle Ages, gardens became smaller and could only be released in religious places such as monasteries. In such places, the water factor was used for the moon and cleanliness and the pools became smaller. At the same time, since they were released on high hills or in areas far from people, the plants planted were mostly edible fruits and vegetables. This situation allowed scientific studies to be conducted and became the beginning of botanical gardens. The first botanical garden established for educational purposes was established in Padua, Italy in 1545. However, there are those who claim that the botanical garden in Pisa, the same country, was planned 2 years before this (Özkan, 2001).

Renaissance gardens were built by taking into account people's desires and expectations. Shaped trees, statues, pergolas and pools were used abundantly here. Terracing and the use of evergreen plants gained predominance. Different period gardens were built that differed from each other in terms of size and magnificence. Florentine Villas are distinguished from the large and rich terraced, statuette, pergola and flamboyant gardens built in Rome by their smallness, simplicity and the sense of comfort they created. Baroc Era gardens, on the other hand, did not care about being opened to the public, disrupted the balance between the plant and the structure and gained a disconnected appearance, sharper and rough-lined geometric shapes were given precedence and the water became stagnant.

Although the gardens built in England were previously built in the Islamic style, the natural green cover of the landscape began to be preferred over time due to the humid climate; artificial roads and walls were demolished, geometric shaped pools were transformed into natural looking ponds. Therefore, the lack of warm climate here led to a change in the structure of the parks and the preferred structures.

In the Turks, gardens were functional because they were lived in, they were not for show; they were places where all kinds of recreational activities could be done. While large western gardens were perceived at a glance, small-scale Turkish gardens had the

opportunity to be perceived over a long period of time with the gradual discovery of their features. Turkish gardens were simple, far from the luxury and magnificence of Greek and Roman gardens, and the residential structure was insignificant next to the garden (Korkut, 1995). However, later the sultans were influenced by the western world and brought new order and magnificence to the gardens. The gardens grew and the structural forms inside them became coarser.

Chinese garden art brought a new understanding by representing the Far East. Unlike Western countries, rocks, stones and sand used next to natural structures were given life and a new order was created. Japanese gardens, which were influenced by this, were established in the same order but included more stunted and crooked trees. In addition, wetlands were surrounded and bridges were included in the garden. Unlike all times, here, magnificence and wealth were not considered important and the welfare of the country was prioritized.

Russian garden art was influenced by all trends and at first it was small in size, then it grew to a grandiose size. Naturalness and surprises were given place in the garden. It was possible to reach different places with secret paths. In later times, exhibitions were held in these gardens and structures representing other cultures were included. At the same time, the establishment of greenhouses allowed the cultivation and research of new plants. This situation allowed the cultivation of plants from different climates in the garden.

Therefore, although the methods, structures and vegetation used in garden art are similar in general terms, they have changed over time depending on the country. This was most affected by the climatic conditions and the culture of that nation. Cultures and nations close to each other have also shown similarities in the development of garden art. Gardens of all times have laid the foundation for the formation of botanical gardens and caused their development.

Botanical gardens have taken their place in a special garden class as one of the important green areas of the urban landscape with various aspects such as having a scientific function, having remarkable designs, taking the preservation of plants as a basis and also providing benefits to nature education (Köse and Gül, 2019).

In other words, botanical gardens, together with garden art, not only increase the importance of plants, habitats and conservation awareness, but also provide visitors with experiences that affect their movements, behaviors and social values (Willison, 1997).

In botanical gardens, Stone gardens, Rock gardens and Rose gardens, which began to be used in garden art in the Far East, can be created by planting suitable plants (Wyman, 1947).

The similarity between the structure of medieval European gardens and Islamic gardens is evident in the establishment of monastery gardens. The predominance of the color green symbolizes life and rebirth here, as in Islamic gardens. Therefore, gardens built in different sizes and designs in many countries and various civilizations throughout the world over the centuries have not only met the desire of people to be in touch with nature, but have also been an indicator of prosperity and power.

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